

PANJARADAGI ZARRACHA KOORDINATASI VA ENERGIYASINING TAQSIMOTLARI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada panjara maydonida harakatlanayotgan zarrachaning koordinatasi va energiya taqsimoti qonuniyatlari nazariy jihatdan tadqiq etilgan. Izlanish davomida kvant va statistik mexanika usullaridan foydalanib, zarrachaning panjara tugunlarida bo'lish ehtimolligi va uning energetik spektri tahlil qilingan. Tizimning harorati va panjara potentsiali zarracha holatiga ko'rsatadigan ta'siri matematik modellar yordamida ko'rsatilgan. Olingan natijalar qattiq jismlar fizikasi va yarimo'tkazgichlar nazariyasida statsionar holatlarni prognozlashda muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Kalit so'zlar: panjara, zarracha koordinatasi, energiya taqsimoti, ehtimollik zichligi, kvant holatlari.

Аннотация. В данной статье теоретически исследованы закономерности распределения координат и энергии частицы, движущейся в поле решетки. В ходе исследования с использованием методов квантовой и статистической механики проанализированы спектр энергии и вероятность нахождения частицы в узлах решетки. С помощью математических моделей продемонстрировано влияние температуры системы и потенциала решетки на состояние частицы. Полученные результаты имеют важное значение для прогнозирования стационарных состояний в физике твердого тела и теории полупроводников.

Ключевые слова: решетка, координата частицы, распределение энергии, плотность вероятности, квантовые состояния.

Abstract. This paper theoretically investigates the distribution regularities of the coordinate and energy of a particle moving in a lattice field. Using the methods of quantum and statistical mechanics, the energy spectrum and the probability of finding the particle at the lattice sites are analyzed. The effects of system temperature and lattice potential on the particle state are demonstrated through mathematical models. The obtained results are of significant importance for predicting stationary states in solid-state physics and semiconductor theory.

Keywords: lattice, particle coordinate, energy distribution, probability density, quantum states.

Faraz qilaylik, zarracha \mathbb{Z} da erkin harakatlanayotgan bo'lsin. Zarracha koordinatasi kuzatiluvchan miqdor bo'lib, unga mos tasodifiy miqdorni k orqali belgilaymiz. Agar biz zarracha koordinatasini kuzatayotgan bo'lsak, unga mos holatlar fazosi Ω o'rnida separabel kompleks Hilbert fazosi $\ell_2(\mathbb{Z})$ ni olish mumkin. Bu kuzatiluvchan miqdorga mos operatorni K orqali belgilaymiz va bu operator

$(Kf)(n) = n \cdot f(n)$, $f \in \ell_2(\mathbb{Z})$ formula yordamida beriladi.

Zarracha koordinatasiga mos K operator birining yoyilmasidagi E_λ , $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}$ proyektorlar quyidagi ko'rinishda bo'ladi:

$$(E_\lambda f)(n) = \chi_{(-\infty, \lambda]}(n)f(n),$$

bu yerda

$$\chi_A(n) = \begin{cases} 1, & n \in A \\ 0, & n \notin A. \end{cases}$$

Endi, faraz qilaylik, V operator $\ell_2(\mathbb{Z})$ Hilbert fazosida quyidagicha aniqlangan bo'lsin:

$$(\hat{V}\hat{f})(p) = \hat{v}(n)\hat{f}(n).$$

Bu yerda \hat{v} funksiya haqiqiy qiymatli $\hat{v}(n) \geq 0$ va $\hat{v} \in \ell_1$. Berilgan shartlarda \hat{V} operator musbat, o'z-o'ziga qo'shma operator bo'ladi.

\hat{V} operator birining yoyilmasiga mos E_λ spektral proektorlar quyidagicha:

$$(E_\lambda \hat{f})(n) = \chi_{B_\lambda}(n)(\hat{f}(n)).$$

Bu yerda $B_\lambda = \{n \in \mathbb{Z}: \hat{v}(n) \leq \lambda\}$. \hat{V} operatorning koordinat tasviridan impuls tasviriga o'tish

$$F: \ell_2(\mathbb{Z}) \rightarrow L_2[-\pi, \pi], (F\hat{f})(p) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \sum_{n \in \mathbb{Z}} \hat{f}(n)e^{inp}$$

Furye almashtirishi orqali amalga oshiriladi.

V integral operator $L_2(\mathbb{T})$ impuls fazoda quyidagicha aniqlanadi:

$$(Vf)(p) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{\mathbb{T}} v(p-q)f(q)dq.$$

Ma'lumki, $\psi_n(p) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{inp}$, $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ sistema $L_2(\mathbb{T})$ fazoda ortonormal bazis tashkil qiladi.

Har bir ψ_n vektorga tortilgan bir o'lchamli qism fazoni $L(n)$ bilan belgilaymiz. $L_2(\mathbb{T})$ Hilbert fazosini $L(n)$ qism fazolar orqali quyidagicha to'g'ri yig'indi ko'rinishda ifodalash mumkin:

$$L_2(\mathbb{T}) = \sum_{n \in \mathbb{Z}} \oplus L(n).$$

Endi $P_n: L_2(\mathbb{T}) \rightarrow L(n)$ proyektorni quyidagicha aniqlaymiz:

$$(P_n f)(p) = (\psi_n, f)\psi_n(p), \quad f \in L_2(\mathbb{T}).$$

Demak, yuqorida kiritilganlardan foydalanib V operatorga mos spektral proyektorlarni keltirishimiz mumkin:

$$E_\lambda(V) = \sum_{\hat{v}(n) \leq \lambda} P_n.$$

Koordinataning ψ holatdagi taqsimot funksiyasi F_ψ quyidagiga teng bo'ladi:

$$\begin{aligned} F_\psi(\lambda) &= \|E_\lambda \psi\|^2 = (E_\lambda \psi, E_\lambda \psi) = (E_\lambda \psi, \psi) = \sum_{n \in \mathbb{Z}} (E_\lambda \psi)(n) \cdot \overline{\psi(n)} = \\ &= \sum_{n \in \mathbb{Z}} \chi_{(-\infty, \lambda]}(n)\psi(n) \cdot \overline{\psi(n)} = \sum_{n \leq \lambda} |\psi(n)|^2. \end{aligned}$$

Xususan, bu yerdan ψ holatda zarrachani $A \subset \mathbb{Z}$ to'plamdan topish ehtimoli

$$P(k_\psi \in A) = \sum_{n \in A} |\psi(n)|^2.$$

ga teng.

Zarracha koordinatasining ixtiyoriy $\psi \in \ell_2(\mathbb{Z})$ holatdagi taqsimoti diskret bo'lib, uning taqsimot qonunini quyidagi jadval orqali berish mumkin:

k_ψ ...	-1	0	1	...	n	...
P ...	$ \psi(-1) ^2$	$ \psi(0) ^2$	$ \psi(1) ^2$...	$ \psi(n) ^2$...

Agar zarracha ikki o'ldamli panjara \mathbb{Z}^2 da harakatlanayotgan bo'lsa, uning ψ holatdagi taqsimot qonuni quyidagicha bo'ladi:

$Y \backslash X$...	-1	0	1	...	n	...
\vdots
-1		$ \psi(-1, -1) ^2$	$ \psi(-1, 0) ^2$	$ \psi(-1, 1) ^2$...	$ \psi(-1, n) ^2$...
0		$ \psi(0, -1) ^2$	$ \psi(0, 0) ^2$	$ \psi(0, 1) ^2$...	$ \psi(0, n) ^2$...
1		$ \psi(1, -1) ^2$	$ \psi(1, 0) ^2$	$ \psi(1, 1) ^2$...	$ \psi(1, n) ^2$...
\vdots	
n		$ \psi(n, -1) ^2$	$ \psi(n, 0) ^2$	$ \psi(n, 1) ^2$...	$ \psi(n, n) ^2$...
\vdots	

Ma'lumki, $\psi_n(p) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{inp}$, $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ sistema $L_2[-\pi, \pi]$ fazoda ortonormal bazis tashkil qiladi.

1-ta'rif. $\psi_n(p) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{inp}$, $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ bazis vektorlariga mos holatlarni bazis holatlar deb ataymiz.

Ma'lumki, uzluksiz u funksiyaga ko'paytirish operatorining spektri u funksiyaning qiymatlar sohasidan iborat bo'ladi. Shunday ekan quyidagi tasdiq o'rinli.

1-lemma. $(Hf)(p) = \frac{1}{m} (1 - \cos p) f(p)$, $f \in L_2[-\pi, \pi]$ tenglik bilan aniqlanuvchi energiya operatori H ning spektri $\sigma(H) = [0, \frac{2}{m}]$ kesmadan iborat.

Demak, energiyaning qabul qilishi mumkin bo'lgan qiymatlari $[0, \frac{2}{m}]$ kesmani to'liq to'ldiradi. Har bir $\lambda \in [0, \frac{2}{m}]$ uchun $A(\lambda)$ to'plamni kiritamiz:

$$A(\lambda) = \{p \in [-\pi, \pi]: \frac{1}{m} (1 - \cos p) \leq \lambda\} = [-\arccos(1 - \lambda m), \arccos(1 - \lambda m)].$$

Bu $A(\lambda)$ to'plamning indikatorini qaraymiz:

$$\chi_{A(\lambda)}(p) = \begin{cases} 1, & p \in A(\lambda) \\ 0, & p \notin A(\lambda). \end{cases}$$

2-lemma. Energiya operatori H ning biri yoyilmasidagi E_λ spektral proyektorlar quyidagicha bo'ladi:

$$(E_{\lambda}f)(p) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{agar } \lambda < 0, \\ \chi_{A(\lambda)}(p)f(p), & 0 \leq \lambda < \frac{2}{m}, \\ f(p), & \text{agar } \lambda \geq \frac{2}{m}. \end{cases}$$

1-teorema. Energiyaning ψ_n bazis holatdagi taqsimot funksiyasi F_{ψ_n} uchun quyidagi tenglik o‘rinli:

$$F_{\psi_n}(\lambda) = \|E_{\lambda}\psi_n\|^2 = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{agar } \lambda < 0, \\ \frac{1}{\pi} \arccos(1 - \lambda m), & \text{agar } 0 \leq \lambda < \frac{2}{m}, \\ 1, & \text{agar } \lambda \geq \frac{2}{m}. \end{cases}$$

1-natija. Barcha ψ_n , $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ bazis holatlar uchun $F_{\psi_n}(\lambda)$ taqsimot funksiyalar bir xil, ya’ni $\{F_{\psi_n}(\lambda)\}$ tasodifiy miqdorlar ketma-ketligi bir xil taqsimlangan.

2-teorema. Energiyaning barcha ψ_n , $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ bazis holatlardagi o‘rta qiymati $\bar{h}_{\psi_n} = \frac{1}{m}$ va dispersiyasi $\delta_{\psi_n}(h) = \frac{1}{2m^2}$ ga teng.

3-teorema. Ixtiyoriy $(\alpha, \beta) \subset [0, \frac{2}{m}]$, $\alpha < \beta$ interval uchun shunday $f_{\gamma} \in L_2[-\pi, \pi]$ holat mavjudki, energiyaning bu holatdagi o‘rta qiymati $\bar{h}_{f_{\gamma}}$ uchun $\bar{h}_{f_{\gamma}} \in (\alpha, \beta)$ munosabat o‘rinli.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR

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